

INSB Class
International Naval Surveys Bureau

MUSICA

Multiple Use of Space for
Island Clean Autonomy

‘Multiple-use-of Space for Island Clean Autonomy’ ‘MUSICA’ G.A. 862252

WP5 – T5.1 [Months: 36]

**D5.1 Plans and test protocols for the sea trial, instrumentation, SCADA
(Preliminary)**

(UofAg,MOC,INSB)

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union Horizon2020 program under the agreement 862252

Document information

<u>Version</u>	<u>Date</u>	<u>Description</u>
<u>1</u>	<u>2024-05-20</u>	<u>Version Draft for approval</u> <u>Prepared by Evangelos Papakonstantinou</u> <u>INSB</u>

Definitions and Abbreviations

MUP	Multiuse Platform
MAWP	Maximum Allowable Working Pressure
OWP	Operational Working pressure
WRES	Wave renewable energy system
HPES	High Pressure Storage System
Hs	Significant wave height
ECU	Energy convention unit of HPES

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Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Standards-guidance and rules	5
3. MUP Structure	6
4. Concrete Structures	7
5. Stationkeeping system - Moorings	7
6. Lashing mounting on the Deck	7
7. Wind turbine	7
8. Hydro pneumatic energy storage HPES system	8
9. Wave RES	9
10. Desalination plan	9
11. Offshore Cable	9
12. Electrical Installations	10
13. Solar PV panels	10
14. The Smoke detection system	10
15. The Ballast system, the Bilge system	11
16. Diesel generator, hydraulic crane	11
17. Autonomous Remote control system	11

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1. Introduction

The deliverable is carrying out an analysis of the tests and trials that should perform for the certification of MUSICA platform. These tests and trials will provide procedures and guidance for the operation and maintenance of the MUP. The test and trials will submit with attached certificates, reports and documentation. These will be included in the operational manual.

Some of the tests defined by the Greek Regulatory framework and required in every case of floating constructions.

Further, the deliverable analyzes the tests and trials required for each equipment. This procedure also will be guided by TRL7 procedures.

The following definitions will be used:

Tests are the examination of equipment or structures required for certification (INSB or authorized by Greek flag workshops)

Trials are the examination of equipment or structures in operation.

Pretrials are Tests and Preliminary Trials before and after laying of the MUP in Shipyard Area
Each equipment provider should issue scenarios for the trials. These scenarios should be validated by the appointed naval architects according to the metocean reported data and further are to be examined by the attending Surveyors.

The MUP will contain the following equipment that will be validated during the Perama Pretrials and Innousses sea trials:

MUP Steel structure

Installation of the equipment and lashing mounting on the Deck

Wind Turbine with capacity up to 800kW

Eight Mooring lines and eight anchors

Innovative storage device on the MUP integrated to Hydro pneumatic energy storage HPES

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Desalination plan

Wave RES with capacity up to 10 kW

Offshore Cable connecting with the grid

Electrical Installations – Batteries

Solar PV panels with capacity up to 60 kW

The Ballast system

The Smoke detection system

The Bilge system

Remote control systems

The attendance in the tests are defined by INSB following the standard procedures and flag requirements the supervisors Naval Architects should be present in most of the trials and tests following the recommendations of INSB.

Some of the trials usually be used for the surveys.

A record sheet should be filled for every test and trial reporting the conditions, results and recommendations. The record sheet is shown in Fig.1 and an example from HPES test could be found in Fig.2

2. Standards-guidance and rules

- ISO 19019 “Sea-going vessels and marine technology — Instructions for planning, carrying out and reporting sea trials”
- ITTC – “Recommended Procedures and Guidelines-Preparation and Conduct of Speed/Power Trials(Limited Guidance)
- ABS-Rules for building and classing mobile offshore units 2018
- IEC 63026 Submarine power cables with extruded insulation and their accessories for rated voltages from 6 kV ($U_m = 7,2$ kV) up to 60 kV ($U_m = 72,5$ kV) –Test methods and requirements

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- IEC 60502 Power cables with extruded insulation and their accessories for rated voltages from 1 kV ($U_m = 1,2 \text{ kV}$) up to 30 kV ($U_m = 36 \text{ kV}$) –Part 2: Cables for rated voltages from 6 kV ($U_m = 7,2 \text{ kV}$) up to 30 kV ($U_m = 36 \text{ kV}$)
- RULES FOR CLASSIFICATION of Ships Edition January 2017 Part 4 Systems and components Chapter 7 Pressure equipment
- ABS RULES FOR BUILDING AND CLASSING MARINE VESSELS - 2024
- ABS GUIDE FOR BUILDING AND CLASSING FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND TURBINES - 2024
- IEC 61400-21-1 “Wind energy generation systems - Part 21-1: Measurement and assessment of electrical characteristics - Wind turbines”

3. MUP Structure

The Manufacturer certificates are to be supplied with the material. Verification of the material’s quality should be done. Welders who are to work on the structure are to be qualified in accordance with the welder qualification tests specified by a recognized code. Welding procedures conforming to the provisions of a recognized code may accepted. Certificates required to be submitted for the above procedures.

A system of nondestructive testing is to be included in the fabrication specification of the structures. The minimum extent of nondestructive testing is to comply with INSB requirements for Nondestructive Inspection or recognized design Code. The test is performed before laying of the MUP by an authorized workshop following Surveyor Guidance. All nondestructive testing records are to be reviewed and approved by the attending Surveyor. The attending Surveyor may request additional nondestructive testing if the quality of fabrication is not conforming to Naval industry standards.

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4. Concrete Structures

Prior to their use in construction, the manufacturers of cement, reinforcing rods, and appliances are to provide documentation of the pertinent physical properties. These data are to be made available to the attending Surveyor for verification of conformity with the properties specified in the approved design.

As applicable, at the construction site, the manufacturer should provide essays following Surveyor's requirements for mechanical strength tests by authorized workshops and reports should be submitted.

5. Stationkeeping system - Moorings

The Physical testing, including break, pull, dimensional and nondestructive testing, is required to be performed in accordance with the submitted specifications by an authorized workshop and to the satisfaction of the attending Surveyor. Supporting documentation should issue for each test by the corresponding workshop for the definition of material, weight, dimensions, breaking load e.t.c. Underwater diver survey should be carried out for the sea bed of the mooring lines during trials

6. Lashing mounting on the Deck

Lashing equipment follow standards, the manufacturer should submit certificates of mechanical properties tests. Mountings should follow rules of classification societies and studies should be submitted for approval.

7. Wind turbine

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The WT are not within the scope of classification, the valid type certificate of the WT are to be examined by the attending Surveyors. Certificates should be submit to INSB for every component of the WT proving the standards followed during construction. The mounting arrangement should be certified for the loads produced by the MUP for all the loading scenarios. Limitations should be defined following the operation of the WT.

The installation of the RNA and tower and the hook-up of the power cable system are not to damage the interface structure to the floating substructure

Further pretrial and trial should be performed following manufacturer guidance and scenarios. Trials or pretrials should performed following IEC-61400-21-1 as far as practical could be applied and following operating limitations described by the operator of the MUP and the design team.

8. Hydro pneumatic energy storage HPES system

All completed pressure vessels should be tested by non-destructive examination of the welds by an authorized workshop and documentation should be submitted.

Pretrial should be performed in the pressure system and the vessels following rules or standard requirements. These pretrial should proceed before installation in a lab and after installation in the yard in Perama.

The final trial should carry out in installation area operating separate and combined with the MUP equipment. The system will be operate in OWP.

Each component of the pressure vessels shall be tested on completion of the work, to at least 1.5 times the MAWP. When all components have been tested as prescribed above, the completed of pressure shall be tested to 1.25 times the MAWP. Hydraulic testing shall be performed in the presence of a surveyor, unless otherwise agreed. The test pressure shall apply and maintain for at least 30 minutes to permit visual examination of all surfaces and joints.

The pretrials as prescribed above, the completed of pressure shall be tested to 1.25 times the MAWP. The duration should be the same. Pretrials for emergency scenarios should be simulated

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in Perama . Pretrials should include the instrumentation, automatic equipment and remote control systems and combination with the other equipment on the MUP.

The trials of pressure vessels will run for at least two (2) hours, the system is to be operated over its full range of pressure to demonstrate the adequacy of all control systems and safety equipment. The emergency scenarios defined for the system should be simulated and run also. Trials should include the instrumentation, automatic equipment and remote control systems and combination with the other equipment on the MUP.

9. Wave RES

Certificates should be submitted for every component of the solar PV panels proving the standards followed during their construction. The trials of wave RES are included in the trials of electrical installations for the electrical part.

10. Desalination plan

Certificates should be submitted for every component of the solar PV panels proving the standards followed during their construction. The trials of wave RES are included in the trials of electrical installations for the electrical part. The management plan of the waste of the desalination plan should be analyzed for the application in MUP installation area in the trials period.

11. Offshore Cable

The offshore cable and all the supporting and operational attached equipment should be tested following the tests in the IEC 63026 standard before installation and reports should be submit to INSB. Lab tests as prescribed in the standard and some should performed attend by INSB surveyor notified by the provider. Certificates should be submitted for every component of the

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submarine power cable and their equipment proving the standards followed during their construction. This equipment could not be performed pretrial in the shipyard so trials should be performed after installation following the above standard. The trials should be voltage tests following paragraph 13 of IEC 63026 standard.

12. Electrical Installations

Certificates should be submitted for every component of the electrical equipment of any installation proving the standards followed during their construction. Pretrials should be performed with shore connection voltage as far as is practicable. The final trials should be performed by powering the circuits with the certified voltage and current, following the schedule of installation of each component.

13. Solar PV panels

Certificates should be submitted for every component of the solar PV panels proving the standards followed during their construction. The trials of solar panels are included in the trials of electrical installations

14. The Smoke detection system

Certificates should be submitted for every component of the smoke detection system proving the standards followed during their construction. Pretrials and trial should be performed by testing sample of detectors after installation.

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15. The Ballast system, the Bilge system

Pressure test of the ballast tanks should be performed in pre-trial period by air. Trial should be performed for the Autonomous operation of this equipment.

16. Diesel generator, hydraulic crane

Certificates should be submitted for diesel generator and hydraulic crane circuits, proving the standards followed during their construction. Manuals also should be submitted for the operation and maintenance of this equipment. Trial should be performed for the Autonomous operation of this equipment.

17. Autonomous Remote control system

Autonomous remote control system is to be assigned to a unit possessing a permanently installed autonomous function. Autonomous function is the automatic remote control and operation of a process, system, or equipment by mechanical or electronic devices that take the place of human labor. These are normally routine or repetitive tasks under predefined scenarios and conditions.

Further, the MUP systems should follow the Autonomous levels in the requirements for autonomous and remote control functions. The trials and pre-trials should be performed in the following levels:

- a. Integration and application loop of Monitoring should be performed by any system
- b. Integration and application loop of Analysis should be performed by any system
- c. Integration and application loop of Decision should be performed by any system
- d. Integration and application loop of Action should be performed by any system

Before pre-trials or trials, the scenarios should be defined for each equipment supervisor and they should be combined in overall scenarios of the MUP supervisors.

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18. Test or Trial record

	Name: Multi Use Platform (MUP)		Date: 10/5/2024	Starting time: 12:00	End time: 13:00
			Area: Perama-Attiki		
			Country: Greece		
Platform condition Draughts: Tcenter= m T1st= m Fore port T2nd= m Fore stbd T3rd= m Aft stbd T4th= m Aft port		Environmental Condition Temp. of air= Celcius Density of sea Water = kg/m ³ Temp. of sea= Celcius Wind speed= m/s Wind BF = BF Wave Height and Direction= m Current= m/s File with air and wave data= Water Depth = m Air Press.=			
Equipment: Hydro-pneumatic Energy Storage -Pelton Turbine					
Test No	Measuring variables				
	Pressure	RPM	Power	Q [c.m./h]	Remarks
Operational items:					
Person in charge for the equipment			Surveyor or attendance		

Fig.1 Record sheet

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	Name: Multi Use Platform (MUP) Pre-Trial	Date:	Starting time:	End time:			
		25/4/2024	10:00	11:00			
		Area:	UoM -Campus				
		Country:	Malta				
Hydro-pneumatic Energy Storage Item HP Pump LP Pump Pelton Turbine		Environmental Conditions on the LAB Temp. of air= 18 Celcius Air Press.= 1 atm					
Equipment: Hydro-pneumatic Energy Storage -Pelton Turbine- HP Pump							
Test No	Measuring variables						Remarks
	Pressure [bar] max	Pressure [bar] min	RPM	Power kW	Q [lt/min] max min		
1	30	10	474		60	60	High pressure Pump
2	30	10	474		60	60	Pipelines-Valves
3	30	0	1000	1	-60	-10	Pelton Turbine
4							PLC operation
5	30	10			60	-60	Manifolds
6				2	180	180	LP Pump
7					180	180	Filter
Conclusions: Lab conditions manually operating the equipment/ Attendance also for PLC use and automation Mr Iain Duane from Neodyne							
Corrective actions:							
Person in charge for the equipment Tonio Sant [UoM]				Surveyor or attendance Papakonstantinou Evangelos [INSB]			

Fig.2 Example of Record sheet from HPES test

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